

Study on Applying Fuzzy AHP and GRA in Selection of Agent Construction Enterprise

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Abstract—To help the client to select a competent agent construction enterprise (ACE), this study aims to investigate the selection standards by using the Fuzzy Analytic Hierarchy Process (FAHP) and build an evaluation mathematical model with Grey Relational Analysis (GRA). According to the outputs of literature review, four orderly levels are established within the model, taking the consideration of various agent construction models in practice. Then, the process of applying FAHP and GRA is discussed in detailed. Finally, through a case study, this paper illustrates how to apply these methods in getting the weights of each standard and the final assessment result.

Keywords—agent construction enterprise, agent construction model, fuzzy analytic hierarchy process, grey relational analysis

I. INTRODUCTION

TO improve the performance of the government investment and to enhance the management of the projects invested by government, Government Document of “Decision about the Reform of Investment System” issued by the China State Council in July 2004 pointed out that China would speed up to apply the agent construction system(ACS)in public project. ACS means that choosing professional project management enterprise by several methods such as bidding to implement construction, and this project management enterprise should control the project investment, the project quality, and the project period strictly, and should transfer the project to the client after the acceptance of completion, see as Fig.1. From then on, the ACS started to be implemented all over the country and it has brought improvements to public projects [1]. However, as the ACS is just in the beginning and improving stage and there is no unified law or regulation in China, some problems have come out about this system , and the selection of agent construction enterprise (ACE) is one of them. The ACE plays the key role in the public project’s success [2], but no unified recognition or law has made definite provisions on how to select the ACE. Researches have been done on this problem, but different researchers put emphasis on different aspect of the selection of ACE. As discussed by Ke [3], the ACE club (directory) can be established based on patterning model from the view of cooperation and trust theory , and the model of selection of ACE by using the external incentive mechanism of

the project is introduced by comparative analysis of bidding and trust selection mechanism based on reputation, suggested by Deng [4]. These studies discuss some problems on how to select the ACE to some extent. However, they fail to give the theoretic analysis of the factors influencing the selection of ACE and any

Fig. 1 Relationship of the Contractual Organization of Agent Construction Project

suggestions. On this condition, the selection method of ACE on the basis of project governance theory is given [5] and the bidding is proposed as a good method, but it also fails to give the suggestion on the operational level. Studies also have been done from the perspective of performance evaluation of ACE [6]–[8]. This is of usefulness after the completion of the project and the directory establishment of ACE, but not so much useful when selecting ACE for a concrete project. As bidding is the main method, how to select ACE by bidding has also been studied by some researchers with many methods, such as the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) [9]–[10], Fuzzy Mathematics and Layered Grey Relational Analysis [11], Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA) [12], and the combination of AHP, FDF and DEA [13]. These give some feasible methods to the selection of ACE. However, these studies do not take the agent construction model into account when selecting ACE, an important consideration for the selection of ACE. As all the agent construction can be divided into three model designed by stage, the different agent construction model has different demands on the ACE. The evaluation system of the previous studies pays less attention to this point. So this paper aims to take the demands of different agent construction model into

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consideration when choosing ACE by bidding. Fuzzy Analytic Hierarchy Process (FAHP) and Grey Relational Analysis (GRA) are used in this research, making the qualitative index quantitative and combining the qualitative analysis and quantitative analysis together. This model not only reflects the demands of the clients of different agent models objectively, but also experts' advices.

II. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research framework could be generalized as four parts. To begin with, a comprehensive literature review which helps to develop a framework for this study was given. It reviewed the previous studies on the selection of ACE, reviewing the achievements have been obtained by researchers in China and making them as the theoretic base of this study. Then the agent construction model was analyzed and the emphasis was put on the agent construction model designed by stage, which was of great importance for the establishment of the indexes system of ACE selection. Based on the agent construction model, the indexes system of ACE selection was established by Fuzzy Analytic Hierarchy Process (FAHP) and Grey Relational Analysis (GRA) was used to build the mathematical model for evaluating the ACE. The FAHP was used to make sure of weight of each standard while (GRA) was employed to choose the best competent ACE. Finally, the finding was given and discussed.

III. AGENT CONSTRUCTION MODEL AND AGENT CONSTRUCTION ENTERPRISE DUTIES

Currently, the model of agent construction project management can be generalized from two aspects: the source of the project capital and the construction stage [14].

Life cycle of a construction project can be divided into the preliminary stage, the design stage, the construction stage and the operational stage. Therefore, the agent construction project management can be designed according to the stage: the non-overall process agent construction and the overall process agent construction. The preliminary agent construction and the implementation stage agent construction are included in the non-overall process agent construction. The non-overall process agent construction is suitable for the project that has high demands on the professional knowledge so as to use the professional advantages of ACE, while the overall agent construction model is suitable for the project that has not so much high demands on the professional knowledge [15]–[16], see Fig. 2.

A. The preliminary stage agent construction

In the preliminary stage, the client entrust the work of project planning, feasibility study, project financing, preliminary design and a part of bidding & contract-award to the ACE who is responsible for the authenticity of the feasibility study report and the project establishment report (see Fig. 2. A). On this condition, the ACE should be very familiar with the capital construction procedure and the preliminary work of the project.

Stage	Preliminary Stage			Design Stage			Construction stage		
	Feasibility study	Project Financing	Preliminary design	Bidding & Contract-award	Detailed Design	Bidding & Contract-award	Preparation	Construction	Transfer
The Preliminary stage		A							
The Implement stage					B				
The overall process				C					

Fig. 2 Agent Construction Model Divided by Stage

B. The implementation stage agent construction

After the feasibility-study report has been approved by authority or the preliminary design has been completed, the project establishes. Then the project enters the implementation stage. The design stage and the construction stage are included in this stage. The project becomes entity from blueprint. In this stage, the client relegates the management of design and construction of the project to the ACE who manages all-round the project according to the approved project establishment report or the preliminary design. The construction standards, the control of project investment, project quality, project period are the core responsibilities of the ACE (see Fig. 2. B).

C. The overall process agent construction

The overall process agent construction (see Fig. 2. C) is that the owner entrusts the management work of the preliminary stage, the design stage and the construction stage to the ACE. A general idea on the construction function, scale, standards and period are given to the ACE and then the ACE is in charge of the feasibility study and manage all-round the project, from the beginning of the project to the transfer of project. As all the works are implemented by one ACE, unnecessary interface management can be reduced to increase the management efficiency. When it comes to this point, this model is suitable for the project that has not so much high demands on the professional knowledge.

IV. ESTABLISHMENT OF THE ACE SELECTION MODEL BASED ON FAHP AND GRA

A. Establishment of the Bidding Evaluation Indexes System

The bidding evaluation indexes system is the key issue. The scientificity and moderation of the target system establishment influence the objectivity and authenticity to the evaluation result of ACE. So, a set of comprehensive and scientific bidding evaluation indexes system is the key.

To achieve this goal, Fuzzy Analytic Hierarchy Process (FAHP) is used to establish the bidding evaluation indexes

system. FAHP is the improved Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP). AHP is a systematic analysis method to analyze the complicated problem and it is widely used in practice. However, there are some problems about AHP: the consistency checkout of the judgment matrix is difficult, the standards for consistency checkout of the judgment matrix are unscientific [17]. So FAHP is put forward to resolve the problem.

Based on the agent model analyze, the bidding evaluation indexes system is established. The demand to the ACE of different agent construction model designed by stage is taken into account so that this model can be appropriate for all the agent construction models.

The FAHP model can be divided into four basic levels: the target level (TL), the standard level (SL), the index level (IL) and the object level (OL), based on the characters of bidding of ACS.

1. Target Level (TL)

The goal of the evaluation is to determine which ACE is competent, so the target should be to choose a competent ACE for the project invested by the government.

2. Standard level (SL) and Index level (IL)

Standard level (SL) and Index level (IL) are the standards used to measure whether the target could be realized. When it comes to the selection of ACE, it means to investigate all the ACEs with the standards comprehensively. As the selection of ACE differs from the selection of contractors, much more emphasis should be paid not only on the tender price but the comprehensive management ability of the ACE. The ACE must be rich of project management experience and ability, especially a good control of investment, quality and schedule. What is most important is that the standards should reflect the demands of the three agent models designed by stage. The demands to the ACE differs [18]. When the client chooses any of the three models, the standards should be applicable. For the preliminary agent model A, the ACE is asked to have a good ability in feasibility study, project financing (if the client can not solve the finance problem), bidding & contract-award, and should be familiar with the capital construction procedure; for the implement agent model B, the ACE must be good at design management, bidding & contract-award, on-site management and comprehensive management; and for the overall process agent model C, here is a high requirement on the ACE that the ACE is demanded to have high ability in the management from the very beginning to the end of the project.

3. Object level (OL)

Object level represents the agent program of each ACE candidate (indicated by ACE).

Based on the analysis, the bidding evaluation indexes system is built (see Fig. 3).

Fig. 3 Bidding evaluation indexes system for the ACE selection

B. Establishment of the Fuzzy Consistent Judgment Matrix

The fuzzy consistent judgment matrix R represents the relative importance of the various factors of one level to the father level. Supposing that standard B has a relationship with the index c_1, c_2, \dots, c_n in the son-level, the fuzzy consistent judgment matrix can be expressed as

$$\begin{array}{c|cccc}
 B & c_1 & c_2 & \dots & c_n \\
 \hline
 c_1 & r_{11} & r_{12} & \dots & r_{1n} \\
 c_2 & r_{21} & r_{22} & \dots & r_{2n} \\
 \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\
 c_n & r_{n1} & r_{n2} & \dots & r_{nn}
 \end{array} \quad (1)$$

where r_{ij} represents the relative importance the index c_i has over c_j when compared with the standard B . The relative importance can be got by adopting the following 0.1—0.9 Quantity Sale.

Now the only answer to this problem from the simultaneous equation above can be gotten as

$$W = [w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n]^T \quad (9)$$

D. Gain of Characteristic Vector Matrix of the Criterion

Supposing that the alternative set $X_i (i = 1, 2, \dots, m)$ is comprised by m participants for the project and the criterion set $x_i (i = 1, 2, \dots, n)$ of the alternative's advantage evaluation comprised by n criterions. Then the characteristic vector matrix of the criterion (decision-making matrix) can be gotten as

$$X = \begin{bmatrix} X_1 \\ X_2 \\ \dots \\ X_m \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} x_{11} & x_{12} & \dots & x_{1n} \\ x_{21} & x_{22} & \dots & x_{2n} \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ x_{m1} & x_{m2} & \dots & x_{mn} \end{bmatrix} \quad (10)$$

1. Ascertainment of the Qualitative and Quantitative Criterion

All the criterions can be divided into either quantitative criterion or qualitative criterion. For the qualitative criterion such as the past experience, the organization team can be evaluated by the linguistic variables and fuzzy number. What linguistic variable differs from numerical variable is that its values are not numbers but words or sentences in a natural or artificial language. Linguistic variables such as "poor management," "good performance," and "moderate risk" describe the vague concept [19]-[21]. Here the Linguistic variables set of the qualitative criterion is established as $E =$ (very good/important, good/important, above average, average, below average, poor/low important, very poor/very low important) in the real-number values ranging in the closed interval between 0 and 1 (see Table II). Let a trapezoidal fuzzy number be parameterized by x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4 , and then the defuzzification value e is given by the following equation [22]:

$$e = (x_1 + x_2 + x_3 + x_4) / 4 \quad (11)$$

The quantitative criterion, such as agent service reward, can be indicated by real amount of money or criterion.

2. The Ascertainment of the Relatively Ideal Alternative

The relative ideal alternative is possible the best competent ACE objectively, getting by selecting the best value of each criterion. In the evaluation criterion, the agent reward is the cost-type criterion which the much smaller the value is the better it is while the organization credit, the ability of management during the preliminary and implementation are benefit-type criterion which the bigger the value is the better it is. It is supposed that the criterion x_{0j} of the relative ideal alternative

X^0 satisfies the following conditions :

$x_j^0 = \min\{x_{1j}, x_{2j}, \dots, x_{mj}\}$ if the criterion is the cost-type criterion

$x_j^0 = \max\{x_{1j}, x_{2j}, \dots, x_{mj}\}$ if the criterion is the

benefit-type criterion

TABLE II
 FUZZY NUMBER FOR LINGUISTIC VARIABLES

very good/ important (VGV/I)	(0.8, 0.9, 1.0, 1.0)
good /important (G/I)	(0.6, 0.7, 0.8, 0.9)
above average (AA)	(0.5, 0.6, 0.7, 0.8)
Average (A)	(0.4, 0.5, 0.6, 0.7)
below average (BA)	(0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.5)
poor/ low important (P/L I)	(0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4)
very poor/ very low important) (VP/VLI)	(0.0, 0.0, 0.1, 0.2)

Then the characteristic vector matrix of the criterion including $n + 1$ alternatives is obtained as

$$\bar{X} = \begin{bmatrix} X_1 \\ X_2 \\ \dots \\ X_m \\ X^0 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} x_{11} & x_{12} & \dots & x_{1n} \\ x_{21} & x_{22} & \dots & x_{2n} \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ x_{m1} & x_{m2} & \dots & x_{mn} \\ x^0_{1j} & x^0_{2j} & \dots & x^0_{mj} \end{bmatrix} \quad (12)$$

3. Normalization of the Characteristic Vector Matrix of the Criterion

Because different evaluation criterions have different dimensions and the value differences between them are obvious, the characteristic vector matrix of the criterion needs to be normalized to eliminate the influence on the decision-making.

For the cost-type criterion, let

$$s_{ij} = (x_{imax} - s_{ij}) / (x_{imax} - s_{imin}) \quad (13)$$

For the benefit-type criterion, let

$$s_{ij} = (x_{ij} - s_{imin}) / (x_{imax} - s_{imin}) \quad (14)$$

After normalization by using (13) and (14), the normalized characteristic vector matrix of the criterion is gotten as

$$S = \begin{bmatrix} s_{11} & s_{12} & \dots & s_{1n} \\ s_{21} & s_{22} & \dots & s_{2n} \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ s_{m1} & s_{m2} & \dots & s_{mn} \\ s^0_{1j} & s^0_{2j} & \dots & s^0_{mj} \end{bmatrix} \quad (15)$$

4. Calculation of the Correlation Degree Index Value

According the GRA, e correlation degree index value r_{ij} between the criterion of the in the decision-making matrix of the alternative i and the criterion j of the relative ideal alternative S^0 is

$$r = \frac{\min_i \min_j |s_{ij} - s_j^0| + \rho \max_i \max_j |s_{ij} - s_j^0|}{|s_{ij} - s_j^0| + \rho \max_i \max_j |s_{ij} - s_j^0|} \quad (16)$$

Where ρ is resolution ratio, $0 < \rho < 1$ generally $\rho = 0.5$.

Based on the equation above the correlation degree index value matrix is gotten as

$$R = \begin{bmatrix} r_{11} & r_{12} & \dots & r_{1n} \\ r_{21} & r_{22} & \dots & r_{2n} \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ r_{n1} & r_{n2} & \dots & r_{nm} \end{bmatrix} \quad (17)$$

5. Calculation of the Correlation Degree Value

The correlation degree is the level for measuring the similarity degree of the index sequence and it ranges in the closed interval between 0 and 1. The closer the value is to 1, the higher the similarity degree of the index sequence has compared to the relative idea alternative. The correlation degree value of each alternative to the relative idea alternative can be gotten as

$$V = R \times W^T = \begin{bmatrix} r_{11} & r_{12} & \dots & r_{1n} \\ r_{21} & r_{22} & \dots & r_{2n} \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ r_{n1} & r_{n2} & \dots & r_{nm} \end{bmatrix} \times \begin{bmatrix} W_1 \\ W_2 \\ \dots \\ W_n \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} v_1 \\ v_2 \\ \dots \\ v_n \end{bmatrix} \quad (18)$$

Sequence the correlation degree value v_i , and chose the alternative with the highest correlation degree value as the most competent ACE for the project.

V. CASE STUDY

A case is studied to illustrate the application of the proposed ACE selection method. The ACS is used in is a municipal facility in Chongqing, China, and this project is the overall process agent construction.

Seven experts are invited to evaluate the relative importance of all the standards. After strict calculation on the weight value, the fuzzy consistent judgment matrix R is got. Next, based on the analysis in section IV, the weights of index can be got by FAHP (see Table III).

TABLE III
WEIGHTS OF THE INDEX

B_i	B_i weighting	C_i	c_i weighting
B1	0.21	C1	0.275
		C2	0.234
		C3	0.156
		C4	0.335
B2	0.23	C5	0.432
		C6	0.568
B3	0.27	C7	0.276
		C8	0.306
		C9	0.254
B4	0.15	C10	0.164
		C11	1.000

B5	0.14	C12	0.285
		C13	0.396
		C14	0.319

And then, the experts evaluate each index of four agent programs (see Table IV).

TABLE IV
LINGUISTIC ASSESSMENT OF EACH AGENT PROGRAM

Program	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6	C7	C8	C9	C10	C11	C12	C13	C14
I	G	VP	G	P	A	AA	P	G	VG	AA	20	G	AA	G
II	VG	G	VG	VG	G	G	BA	G	A	A	26	P	G	A
III	A	VG	BA	VG	A	VG	A	AA	A	VP	23	P	P	A
IV	BA	G	A	G	A	VG	VP	G	G	A	18	VG	VG	A

C11 represents the Agent service reward and the unit of it is million CNY.

Through Table IV, the characteristic vector matrix of the criterion can be got as

$$X = \begin{bmatrix} 0.75 & 0.075 & 0.75 & 0.25 & 0.55 & 0.65 & 0.25 & 0.75 & 0.9 & 0.65 & 20 & 0.75 & 0.65 & 0.75 \\ 0.9 & 0.75 & 0.9 & 0.9 & 0.75 & 0.75 & 0.35 & 0.75 & 0.55 & 0.55 & 26 & 0.25 & 0.75 & 0.55 \\ 0.55 & 0.9 & 0.35 & 0.9 & 0.55 & 0.9 & 0.55 & 0.65 & 0.55 & 0.075 & 23 & 0.25 & 0.25 & 0.55 \\ 0.35 & 0.75 & 0.55 & 0.75 & 0.55 & 0.9 & 0.075 & 0.75 & 0.75 & 0.55 & 18 & 0.9 & 0.9 & 0.55 \end{bmatrix}$$

And then through the GRA method introduced before, the correlation degree index value matrix is gotten as

$$R = \begin{bmatrix} 0.63 & 0.33 & 0.63 & 0.33 & 0.33 & 0.33 & 0.36 & 1 & 1 & 0.7 & 0.63 & 0.63 & 0.56 & 1 \\ 1 & 0.63 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 0.45 & 0.42 & 1 & 0.33 & 0.56 & 0.33 & 0.33 & 0.63 & 0.33 \\ 0.42 & 1 & 0.33 & 1 & 0.33 & 1 & 0.56 & 0.33 & 1 & 0.33 & 0.42 & 0.33 & 0.33 & 0.33 \\ 0.33 & 0.63 & 0.42 & 0.63 & 0.33 & 1 & 0.33 & 1 & 0.5 & 0.56 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 0.33 \end{bmatrix}$$

According to (18), the correlation degree value v_i of each agent program can be got as

$$v = [v_1 \ v_2 \ v_3 \ v_4]^T = [0.576 \ 0.637 \ 0.579 \ 0.698]$$

namely $v_4 > v_2 > v_3 > v_1$, it indicates that the agent program IV is closest to the relative ideal alternative program, so the ACE IV is the competent ACE. In practice, the agent construction project was entrusted to the ACE IV. At present, the project has been completed and the project is well done in the whole process. In this case, the ACE IV can be said to be a competent ACE.

VI. CONCLUSION

The ACE plays the key role in the public project's success and the selection of the ACE is an important issue of the ACE. But no unified law has been made on how to select the ACE. So there is a need to explore appropriate methods on how to select the most competent ACE for the projects invested by government. Based on the existing researches, this paper established the bidding evaluation indexes system for the ACE selection based on the agent construction model designed by stage with FAHP and the mathematical model with GRA, which would help the government to select the best competent ACE for the public project in China.

1) The established bidding evaluation indexes system for the ACE selection in this paper is applicable for all the agent construction models designed by stage. One hand, as all the agent construction projects always can be divided by stage and

the certain project is either the non-overall process agent construction model or the overall process agent construction model, this index system is universal to this point. On the other hand, this index system could also reflect the different demands on the ACE obviously.

2) Through the analysis of the index system, the Grey Relational Analysis was employed to build the mathematical model for selecting the best competent agent construction enterprise. This model is a combination of the qualitative analysis and quantitative analysis, not only reflecting many factors for the evaluation of ACE objectively but adopting the experts' opinions.

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